

Deploying Configurable and Containerized Science Gateways

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ABSTRACT

The challenges in building science gateways are as varied as the problems they seek to solve, and there is no guarantee that the obstacles of tomorrow will look anything like the challenges of today. To meet the ever-changing needs of researchers, gateways must be rapidly deployable, easy to customize, and yet consistent enough that researchers can intuitively understand and use them.

At Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), a variety of science gateways are used by researchers to access TACC's computing resources, manage data and collaborate with other researchers. First generation portals were deployed directly to a virtual machine and suffered from a slew of issues over time such as package conflicts, difficulties in allowing for customization and brittle deployments caused by VM upgrades (e.g security updates). To address these challenges, the services of science gateways - such as a user guide, content management system (CMS), dashboard and other applications - were separated into Docker containers hosting distinct services. We then developed a Docker container-based deployment framework called Camino to facilitate the deployment [1]. The Camino framework employs configuration settings stored in a repository to facilitate easy, transparent and reproducible deployments. With this approach, developers can easily customize and deploy upgrades at-will to individual containers, meeting the rapidly evolving needs of PIs and stakeholders.

Camino is currently used to deploy and manage a multitude of scientific gateways at TACC. As an example, these gateways are typically centered around our core science gateway, a Django/React application called Core-Portal [2] which provides a dashboard to HPC job access, data access, and collaboration tools, and runs in its own isolated container.

Join us for this lightning talk where we will share the tools, strategies, and real-world solutions we are building now for the challenges of tomorrow. Whether the needs require a science gateway for documentation, or one that can interface with storage and HPC resources, come learn about the tooling and strategies we use to deliver customizable on-demand gateways. We will present the tech we use and describe the strategies and software design philosophies we are implementing to generate composable, extendable gateways that can deliver everything from full-fledged multi-service solutions to a-la-carte style service selection.

Keywords— *containers; docker; gateway; services; frontend; backend; deployment; continuous; infrastructure*

REFERENCES

- [1] Camino: <https://github.com/TACC/Camino>
- [2] Core-Portal: <https://github.com/TACC/Core-Portal>